

A METHOD OF IN-PLANE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TEST FOR CFRP

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Summary

A method of in-plane fracture toughness test for CFRP is proposed in this paper. A new SEN tension specimen and the loading grip system are developed for the extremely anisotropic materials such as CFRP. A personal computer program is developed in order to calculate the effect of anisotropy on the stress intensity factor, K , of the SEN tension specimen. The program is applied to the calculation of K_Q from the critical load at crack propagation. An a.c. electrical potential drop measuring system with temperature compensation circuit is developed and applied to determination of the crack initiation. The carbon/epoxy [0/90] laminates are used in the in-plane fracture toughness test. A procedure for the evaluation of fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , is proposed based on the relation between K_Q and the electrical potential drop at the crack propagation.

Introduction

The applicability of the linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) to metallic alloys, which may be assumed as homogeneous isotropic materials, has been well established. The test method of plane strain fracture toughness K_{IC} of heavy section of metallic alloys is standardized in ASTM E-399 in the condition of small scale yielding. Recently many reports are published in which the applicability of LEFM to CFRP is discussed, for example, (1)-(5). CFRP is an inhomogeneous and extremely anisotropic material and its fracture process near crack tip is very complicated. It is difficult to apply the usual method of fracture toughness test, which is based on homogeneous isotropic LEFM.

The present discussion is concerned with development of a method of in-plane fracture toughness test which is applicable to the inhomogeneous anisotropic materials such as CFRP. The problems discussed in this paper can be summarized as follows;

- (1) Development of a new SEN tension specimen and a loading grip system
- (2) Analysis of stress intensity factor of orthotropic materials
- (3) Development of detection method of crack initiation by using a.c. electrical potential drop technique

Specimen and Loading Grip System

Compact specimen and 3-point bend specimen are commonly used for metallic alloys in the fracture toughness test. CFRP is often used in the form of thin plate and if we apply compact specimen or 3-point bend specimen to thin CFRP plate, the specimen easily takes place the buckling failure in the compressive region of the ligament before the crack initiation. In the paper the single-edge notched (SEN) tension specimen is used in order to avoid the buckling failure of a thin plate.

SEN tension specimen is usually loaded by pins in order to apply unidirectional tensile load with respect to center line of specimen. But CFRP specimens often break at holes during the test. The alternative loading system is developed. The configurations of the new SEN tension specimen and the developed grip system are shown in Figures 1 and 2 respectively.

The New SEN Tension Specimen

As shown in Figure 1, the tabs of the specimen are made of GFRP and the specimen is clamped by the pairs of wedges of the special grip system. The center line of the specimen can be held in alignment with the load line by using a pair of small holes at the tabs. The crack-like notch is induced by a grinding cutter, whose width and root diameter are approximately 0.3 mm. The crack length, a , is 25 mm and the crack depth ratio, a/W , is 0.5.

Figure 1 - Single-edge notched (SEN) tension specimen which is developed for the fracture toughness test of extremely anisotropical plate such as CFRP.

The Loading Grip System Developed

Each wedge in the grip system has an axis and a bearing as shown in Figure 2, and the gripping faces can rotate with respect to the center on the load line. By using the mechanism, the bending moment is always zero

Figure 2 - Loading grip mechanism which can apply unidirectional tensile load to the SEN specimen.

with respect to the center line of the specimen during the test. The unidirectional tensile load is applied to the asymmetrically deformed SEN tension specimen with an edge crack. The load condition of the test system is very simple and it is of great advantage both to execution of fracture toughness test and to analysis of the experimental data.

Analysis of Stress Intensity Factor

Method of Calculation

The SEN tension specimen subjected to the uniform tensile stress and concentrated unidirectional load is calculated by using the 2 dimensional finite element method (FEM). The rectangular coordinate systems of (X,Y) and (1,2) are shown in Figure 3. The path independent integral, J, proposed by Rice (6), is evaluated,

$$J = \int_{\Gamma} \left(W dy - T(dw/dx) ds \right) \quad (1)$$

where, x and y are rectangular coordinates normal to the crack front, y being perpendicular to the crack surface; W is the elastic strain energy density; \vec{T} is the traction vector; \vec{u} is the displacement vector; ds is an increment of arc length along any contour, Γ , beginning along the bottom surface of the crack and ending along the top surface as shown in Figure 4. J integral is equivalent to the energy

Figure 3 - SEN tension specimen is analysed numerically. It is subjected to uniform tensile stress and concentrated unidirectional load. Rectangular coordinate systems (1,2) and (x,y) are shown in this figure.

release rate ,G, in the elastic body. When the material is assumed to be orthotropic with the crack on one plane of symmetry, the J-integral can be converted into the stress intensity factor, K_I (7).

$$K_I = \sqrt{E'J} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{E'} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2E_xE_y}} \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{E_y} - \nu_x + \frac{E_x}{2G_{xy}}} \quad (3)$$

By using Eqs.(1)-(3), K_I is able to be obtained. FEM is used in order to calculate the path integral of Eq.(1) numerically.

Figure 4 - Coordinate system near crack tip and contour of J integral.

Normalized Stress Intensity Factor

The independent elastic moduli of 2-dimensional orthotropic material are E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} and ν_1 . The subscript 1 and 2 represent the rectangular coordinates, 1 being parallel to the load direction as shown in Figure 3. But from the consideration of Airy's potential;

$$(1/E_1)\partial_2^4 F + (1/G_{12} - 2\nu_1/E_1)\partial_1^2 \partial_2^2 F + (1/E_2)\partial_1^4 F = 0 \quad (4)$$

the stress distribution of the orthotropic material is determined by two normalized parameters, β_1 and β_2 .

$$\beta_1 = E_2 / E_1 \quad \beta_2 = E_1 / G_{12} - 2\nu_1 \quad (5)$$

as the results, the normalized stress intensity factor, F_I , can be obtained by Eq.(6),

$$F_I = \frac{K_I B W}{\sqrt{a} P} = F_{ISO}(\lambda) \cdot F_A(\lambda, \beta_1, \beta_2) \quad (6)$$

where B is thickness of specimen; W is width; a is crack length; P is load and $\lambda = a/W$ is the crack depth ratio. $F_{ISO}(\lambda)$ is the normalized stress intensity factor of isotropic SEN tension specimen(8),

$$F_{ISO}(\lambda) = 1.19 - 0.41\lambda + 18.70\lambda^2 - 38.48\lambda^3 + 53.85\lambda^4 \quad (7)$$

$F_A(\lambda, \beta_1, \beta_2)$ represents the normalized factor of orthotropy. In the investigation, the results of $F_A(\lambda, \beta_1, \beta_2)$ are obtained in the range of

$$0.45 \leq \lambda \leq 0.55, \quad 0.005 \leq \beta_1 \leq 100 \quad \text{and} \quad -3 \leq \beta_2 \leq 200$$

the interpolative expression of Eq.(7) is represented as a basic program and the stress intensity factor of orthotropic SEN tension specimen can be easily calculated by the personal computer.

a.c. Electrical Potential Drop Method

The crack initiation of CFRP can be detected with a high accuracy by

Figure 5 - a.c. electrical potential drop method with temperature compensation circuit is applied to fracture toughness test of CFRP.

the a.c. electrical potential drop (a.c. electrical P.D.) method, in which the change of electric resistance of the specimen with crack propagation is measured. As the carbon fiber is a good conductor but the matrix is usually an insulating material, the selective detection of crack propagation with fiber breaking is possible by using the a.c. P.D. method.

The block diagram of a.c. P.D. system is shown in Figure 5. The two sine waves which are generated by the variable 2-phase function generator are amplified and the a.c. constant current is applied to the specimen and the dummy specimen simultaneously in order to compensate the electrical disturbance due to temperature. The electrical potential difference is measured by the rock-in amplifier, in which the signal with the exactly same frequency of a.c. current source is measured selectively. The high stability and the high detection sensitivity are obtained by using the temperature compensation circuit and the rock-in amplifier.

Table 1 - Specification and mechanical properties of the laminate

No.	1	2	3	4	5
Prepreg	TORAY P305/25				
Cure Condition	135 C 980 kPa 60 min.				
Laminate	(0 ₄)s	(0 ₂ /90/0)s	(0/90/0/90)s	(90 ₂ /0/90)s	(90 ₄)s
Thickness mm	2.23	2.00	2.07	2.04	2.04
V _f %	59.4	59.6	56.8	58.4	59.6
Tensile Strength MPa	1680		788	369	57.2
Elongation %	(1.32)		1.13	1.03	0.67
Young's Modulus GPa	127	96	69	37	8.8
Transverse Shear Strength MPa			71.6		

(a) ST-1 specimen

(b) ST-2 specimen

(c) ST-3 specimen

(d) ST-4 specimen

(e) ST-5 specimen

Figure 6 - Examples of load and P.D. versus COD. P.D. increases very sharply at the crack initiation with fiber break.

Materials and Test Procedure

The carbon/epoxy [0/90] laminates are used for the in-plane fracture toughness test. $V_f(90)/[V_f(0)+V_f(90)]$ are chosen 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1. the CFRP plates were prepared using a hot-press technique from TORAY P305/25 prepreg. The nominal single-ply thickness and specimen thickness are 0.25 mm and 2 mm respectively. Fiber volume fraction $V_f=V_f(0)+V_f(90)$ of the produced laminates were 57% - 60%. The specification and the mechanical properties of the laminates are represented in Table 1. The SEN tension specimen as shown in Figure 1 are prepared for the test.

The electrode sets for a.c. P.D. and the clip-on gage are attached to the specimen in order to monitor the P.D. and the crack opening displacement (COD). The unidirectional tensile load is applied to the specimen through the developed grip system by the MTS electro-hydraulic test facility. The frequency of a.c. is 2 kHz and the initial P.D. is 300 mV.

Test Results

Figures 6(a) to (e) show the examples of load (P) and electrical potential (E.P.) versus COD. The identification number of the specimen followed by ST- coincides with the number of laminate in Table 1. ST-2-4 specimen, for example, is made from the laminate No.2 [0₂/90/0]s. In the case of ST-1, the crack propagates through the matrix in the direction of fiber. The crack path is normal to the initial crack. The change of P.D. is not sharp because the crack propagates without fiber braking. But the crack initiation is supposed to occur near the load level of 2 kN, where P.D. increases rather rapidly. The final maximum load of ST-1 specimens reaches 85 kN.

In the case of ST-2 to ST-4, the crack propagates with fiber breaking. The crack path is parallel to the initial crack direction from the macroscopic view point. The P.D. increases very sharply at the crack initiation with fiber break. The P.D. technique is very useful for the detection of crack propagation of CFRP. But in the case of ST-5, the specimens break easily at very low load. The crack propagates through matrix in parallel direction of fiber. The P.D. increases at the final break point and it is difficult to detect the crack initiation. For convenience sake, the experimental values of K_Q for ST-5 specimens are measured as the stress intensity factor at the maximum load.

Discussion

The stress intensity factor, K_Q , at the critical load is calculated by using the computer code developed in this paper. The critical load is determined as the load at which the first crack propagation occurs. The amount of scatter of each type of specimens is illustrated in Figure 7. The variation of K_Q mainly depends on the length of crack propagation. Figures 8(a), (b) and (c) show the relation between K_Q and P.D. change at K_Q of ST-2, 3 and 4 specimens respectively. A close relation is observed between them. The fracture toughness, K_c , at P.D.=0 is extrapolated by using the least squares method. Defined in this manner, K_c gives a lower bound of

Figure 7 - Variation of K_Q of ST-1 to ST-5.

(a) ST-2 specimen

(b) ST-3 specimen

(c) ST-4 specimen

Figure 8 - Relation between K_Q and P.D. change at Crack initiation. Close relation is observed between them. K_c at P.D.=0 is extrapolated by using the least squares method.

Table 2 - Result of fracture toughness K_c of CFRP. carbon/epoxy [0/90] laminates shown in Table 1 are tested.

Laminate No.	1	2	3	4	5
K_c MPa√m	17.3	96.5	37.5	24.6	1.95

the experimental data of K_Q . The results of K_c are summarized in Table 2.

Conclusions

The new SEN tension specimen and the loading grip system are developed for the in-plane fracture toughness test of CFRP. The stress intensity factor of the orthotropic SEN tension specimen is analysed numerically by using the finite element method. A personal computer program is developed in order to calculate the effect of orthotropy on the stress intensity factor of SEN tension specimen which is used in the test. The a.c. P.D. method with the temperature compensation circuit is successfully applied to the detection of the crack initiation of CFRP. 5 types of carbon/epoxy [0/90] laminates are used in the in-plane fracture toughness test and the close relation between K_Q and the electrical P.D. is obtained. A procedure for the evaluation of fracture toughness, K_c , is proposed based on the relation between K_Q and P.D. at the crack initiation.

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